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2 Title **Influence of the dry yeast preparation method on final sparkling wine**
3 **characteristics**

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12 **Abstract:** The effect of preparing the commercial yeast *prise de mousse S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007 on the second fermentation kinetics of a Macabeo white base wine was evaluated. The influence of yeast preparation on final “Cava” sparkling wines was determined. The medium glucose, peptone, yeast extract (GPY medium) and the characteristic classic *ped de cuve* procedure were used to prepare the inoculum, which was placed, besides a tirage liqueur, inside bottles in which a second fermentation took place by the “traditional method”. The fermentation kinetics was similar for the first 60 days regardless of the employed yeast inoculum preparation. In both cases, glucose was exhausted and a few grams of fructose remained on day 30. The ethanol concentration after 60 days was the same in all the lines. The sparkling wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeasts showed higher titratable acidity, lower total polysaccharide and protein contents, and greater foamability (HM) and foam stability (HS). Regarding volatile compounds, these wines contained higher esters, fatty acids, higher alcohols and γ -butyrolactone. Differences in wines’ visual and flavor attributes were not significant no matter what inoculum was used. However, the aroma score was significantly higher in the wines inoculated with the *ped de cuve*-prepared yeasts.

13 **Keywords:** *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; sparkling wine; “Cava” wine; second fermentation; *ped de cuve*; volatile compounds; foam; polysaccharides; proteins

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1. Introduction

Sparkling wine production by the “traditional method” requires two successive alcoholic fermentations (AFs). First, fermentation was regular white winemaking that results in dried wine to be bottled. A mixture of sugars and yeasts (tirage liqueur) and riddling agents (usually bentonite) is added to each bottle to perform a second fermentation inside capped bottles. This fermentation runs at low temperature (12–15°C) and takes 14–45 days. The main consequences are a slight increase in ethanol (around 1.4 degrees) and considerable CO₂ gain, which dissolves in wine and increases the pressure inside bottles.

42 The second fermentation is followed by an aging period during which wine remains in
43 contact with dead yeast cells and undergoes a process called autolysis (see Kemp, *et al.*
44 [1]). Yeast autolysis can be defined as irreversible enzymatic degradation of cell compo-
45 nents and occurs after cell death [2]. Degraded components are slowly released to extra-
46 cellular media to, thus, modify sparkling wine composition and its organoleptic charac-
47 teristics: roundness, flavor, complexity and foaming [3,4].

48 High-quality sparkling wines, such as “Champagne” (France), “Cava” (Spain) or
49 “Talento” (Italy), are fermented in closed bottles following the “traditional method” or
50 the AOC Champagne “Champenoise” method (described above), and remain in contact
51 with yeast lees in bottles for several months, and even years [5].

52 Winemakers generally use active commercial dried yeast to perform the second fer-
53 mentation. Sometimes the yeast used for this secondary fermentation is the same as that
54 employed for the first one. Invariably however, this yeast must be chosen for its ability to
55 ferment high-acidity and low-pH wines and must be ethanol-tolerant [4,6]. To overcome
56 the harsh conditions inside bottles (low pH, ethanol and low sugar content, rising CO₂
57 pressure), dry yeast must be adapted to ensure that fermentation is successfully com-
58 pleted. One of the methodologies for adaptation involves the culture of the selected yeast
59 in several media that contain increasing ethanol concentrations. This adaptation process
60 is known as *piéd de cuve* [7].

61 Research into sparkling wine production has focused mostly on aging and autolysis
62 by analyzing changes in polysaccharides, oligosaccharides and nitrogenous compounds
63 during the aging period [8,9]. Many studies have also evaluated the influence of different
64 factors (e.g. yeast strain, base wine, production method, aging time) on the aromatic pro-
65 file and sensory properties of sparkling wines [3,10-12]. However, very few research
66 works have studied the influence of yeast inoculation or preparation procedures on both
67 secondary fermentation kinetics, the volatile compound and sensorial attributes of spar-
68 kling wines [3,7,13]. Yeast inoculated to perform secondary fermentation faces different
69 stressful conditions: high CO₂ pressure, ethanol, low pH, scarce nutrients, etc. Kunkee and
70 Ough [14] report that pressure is most inhibitory to growth, especially at a low pH or a
71 high alcohol concentration. This inhibition diminishes when yeast cells are adapted to
72 wine before inoculation, which reveals the need for previous yeast preparation. Adapting
73 yeast cells to ethanol results in a larger and more viable population [15]. Laurent and Va-
74 lade [16] analyzed the effect of adding nitrogen (N) to *piéd de cuve* in both adaptation and
75 proliferation steps. They conclude that N addition produces a bigger biomass and faster
76 sugar consumption in media. Martí-Raga, Martín, Gil, Sancho, Zamora, Mas and Beltran
77 [3] showed that inorganic N or inactive dry yeast addition in yeast proliferation steps sig-
78 nificantly influences the pressure gain during the second fermentation.

79 For routine yeast growing, culture media like glucose-peptone-yeast (GPY) extract
80 broth is used in laboratories. GPY has organic N sources, such as peptone and yeast ex-
81 tract, that promote rapid growth and a large cell final biomass, and also act as protective
82 agents in the adaptation and proliferation steps of the yeast starter culture before the sec-
83 ond fermentation in sparkling wines. Johansson, *et al.* [17] demonstrated that *S. cerevisiae*
84 grown on a medium consisting in a mixture of spent sulfite liqueur (SSL) and a medium
85 containing glucose yeast extract and (NH₄)₂SO₄ (YD) produces more ethanol than when
86 grown on SSL or YD.

87 The main objective of this study was to investigate the influence of the preparation
88 method of the commercial *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007 dry yeast on fermentation kinetics,
89 foaming properties and other parameters related to autolysis, and also on the volatile
90 composition of sparkling wines after 9 months of aging. The effects of the two yeast pre-
91 preparation methodologies on the fermentation kinetics, the foaming properties and the pa-
92 rameters related to yeast autolysis on both volatile composition and on sensorial proper-
93 ties of the finished sparkling wines were studied.

94 2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Microorganisms and yeast starter culture preparation

The commercial yeast for *prise de mousse* *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007 (Institute Oenologique de Champagne, Reims, France) was used to accomplish the second fermentation of sparkling wines. The IOC 18-2007 yeast was prepared following two different methodologies. Dry yeast was prepared in two ways: a) by a *pied de cuve* methodology at the winery; b) using the routine medium (GPY) in the laboratory. The *pied de cuve* preparation comprises different steps: first, a tirage liqueur was prepared by adding 50 kg of sucrose to 1200 L of base wine (80% Macabeo and 20% Chardonnay). Components were mixed and kept at 20°C; second, 1 kg of yeast IOC 18 2007 was rehydrated in 10 L of water at 37°C. To this blend, 1 kg of the Fortifrem yeast nutrient (Lallemand, Inc., Montreal, QC, Canada) was added and mixed for 15 minutes; third, every 10 minutes, 10% tirage liqueur was added to the previously prepared yeast solution. Maintaining the difference in temperature between the yeast solution and the tirage liqueur below 10°C was important; fourth, O₂ (10 mL/L, once a day) was added to the mixture and left at 20°C for 3 days. After this time, yeast cells had grown and fermentation had started. At this time, a microscopic cell count was done to calculate the *pied de cuve* volume needed to obtain a concentration of 1.5x10⁶ cells/mL inoculum in the bottle. Alternatively, the IOC 18-2007 yeast was rehydrated directly in GPY [18] at a concentration of 10% (w/v), and maintained at 37°C for 1 h in the laboratory. Later the yeast was inoculated in fresh GPY and incubated overnight at 25°C to reach 2x10⁸ CFU/mL. The laboratory-prepared culture was transported to the winery and used to inoculate the base wine at the same concentration as the yeast prepared by *pied de cuve* in the winery.

2.2 Sparkling wine production and sampling times

Vinification trials were run with a base wine that consisted in a coupage of 80% Macabeo and 20% Chardonnay base wines at a winery of the Denominación de Origen Protegida (D.O.P., Designation of Protected Origin) Utiel-Requena, Spain. The second fermentation was performed by the “traditional method” (inside capped bottles) according to EU and Spanish government specifications [19,20]. The base wine (1 g/L reducing sugars; 11% ethanol v/v; pH 3.15; titratable acidity 8.50 g/L, expressed as tartaric acid; volatile acidity 0.16 g/L, expressed as acetic acid) was distributed inside transparent glass bottles. The tirage liqueur was prepared to obtain a final concentration of 12 g/L glucose and 12 g/L of fructose in the final blend, and the yeast starter culture was prepared as *pied de cuve* at the winery or grown in GPY in the laboratory to be added to obtain 1.5x10⁶ cells/mL in the bottle (2 mL GPY culture or 15 mL *pied de cuve* were added to 750 mL bottle of the base wine). Bottles were kept at 11-13°C and a relative humidity of 75-85% for 9 months. Twenty-four bottles per experiment were inoculated. All the bottles were analysed along the second fermentation to accomplish the different objectives (kinetics of sugar consumption and ethanol production, chemical characteristics of sparkling wines, parameters related to yeast autolysis and foaming properties, volatile aroma analysis and sensory analysis). Every week for the first month, at the end of the second month and at 9 months aging, three bottles per experiment were opened to determine glucose, fructose and ethanol concentrations to know the second alcoholic fermentation kinetics. High-Pressure Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) quantified both sugars and ethanol (see below). The volatile composition of the resulting sparkling wines was determined by Gas Chromatography at the end of the aging period (9 months). Before the analysis, bottles were riddled and disgorged. Brut nature sparkling wines were obtained and no expedition liqueur was added. Experiments were performed in triplicate.

2.3 Analytical methods

The glucose, fructose and ethanol contents were quantified by HPLC (Agilent series 1200 system, Agilent Technologies, Barcelona, Spain), equipped with an isocratic pump (Agilent G1310A), following the procedure described by Frayne [21], with minor modifications. The mobile phase consisted of a solution of 0.75 mL of 85% H₃PO₄ (Panreac, Castellar del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain) per liter of deionized water at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min.

148 An Agilent G1322A degasser was employed. Samples (5 μ L) were automatically injected
149 (Agilent G1367B). Compounds were separated in an Aminex HPX-87H precolumn (Bio-
150 Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) coupled with two ion exclusion columns of 300 mm by 7.8 mm,
151 Aminex HPX-87H (Bio-Rad), which were thermostatically controlled at 65°C (Agilent
152 G1316A). Compounds were detected by a G1314B variable-wavelength detector (Agilent)
153 set at 210 nm and a refractive index detector (Agilent G1362A) set in series. The elution
154 time was 45 min. External calibration was performed with the reference standards of glu-
155 cose, fructose and ethanol (Panreac). All the samples were centrifuged at 6000 g for 10 min
156 (PrismR centrifuge, Labnet, Madrid, Spain). Then the supernatant was filtered through a
157 membrane filter with a mean pore size of 0.22 μ m before injection (Labbox, Premià de
158 Dalt, Barcelona, Spain). Quantification was performed by measuring the peak height com-
159 pared to those of the external standards.

160 The analytical methods recommended by the OIV were used to determine titratable
161 acidity and volatile acidity [22]. pH was determined by a Hanna Instruments HI 8424 pH
162 meter (Smithfield, RI, USA). Foaming, proteins and polysaccharides measurements were
163 taken as described by Canals, *et al.* [23], Ayestarán, *et al.* [24] and Maujean, *et al.* [25].

164 2.4 Volatile aroma compound analysis and Odor Activity Value (OAV) estimation

165 Volatile compounds were analyzed by the procedure proposed by Ortega, *et al.* [26]
166 with slight modifications. A volume of 2.7 mL of the samples was transferred to a 10-mL
167 screw-capped centrifuge tube containing 4.05 g of ammonium sulfate (Panreac), to which
168 the following compounds were added: 6.3 mL of milliQ water (Panreac), 20 μ L of standard
169 internal solution (2-butanol, 4-methyl-2-pentanol and 2-octanol from Aldrich (St. Louis,
170 MO, USA), at 140 μ g/mL each, in absolute ethanol from LiChrosolv-Merck (Darmstadt,
171 Germany), and 0.25 mL of dichloromethane (LiChrosolv-Merck). The tube was shaken
172 mechanically for 120 min and then centrifuged at 2900 g for 15 min. The dichloromethane
173 phase was recovered with a 0.5-mL syringe (Labbox) transferred to the autosampler vial
174 and analyzed. The chromatographic analysis was carried out in a HP-6890 (Hewlett Pack-
175 ard, San José, CA, USA), equipped with a ZB-Wax plus column (60 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25
176 μ m) from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). The column temperature, initially set at 40°C
177 and maintained at this temperature for 5 min, was raised to 102°C at a rate of 4°C/min, to
178 112°C at a rate of 2°C/min and to 125°C at a rate of 3°C/min, and then this temperature
179 was maintained for 5 min before being raised to 160°C at a rate of 3°C/min; to 200°C at
180 a rate of 6°C/min. Finally, this temperature was kept for 30 min. The carrier gas was helium
181 (Carbueros Metálicos, Massalfassar, Valencia, Spain), which was fluxed at a rate of 3
182 mL/min. The injection was done in the split mode 1:20 (injection volume 2 μ L) with a
183 flame-ionization-detector (FID detector, Hewlett Packard).

184 In addition, Kovats retention indices (KI) were calculated for the GC peaks corre-
185 sponding to identify the substance by the interpolation of the retention time of normal
186 alkane (C8 –C20) (Fluka Buchs, Schwiez, Switzerland), analyzed under the same chroma-
187 tographic condition. The calculated KI were compared to those reported in the literature
188 for the same stationary phase.

189 2.5 Parameters related to yeast autolysis and foaming properties

190 To determine the total protein content of the finished sparkling wines, samples were
191 concentrated following a two-step dialysis in tubes with an MM cut-off of 3.5 kDa (Merck,
192 Darmstadt, Germany) and were then lyophilized (Virtis manifold benchtop freeze dryer,
193 Virtis Co. Inc., Gardner, NY, USA) and frozen at -20°C. The lyophilized samples were
194 resuspended in 0.6 μ L of ammonium acetate solution (300 mmol/L) (Panreac) and centri-
195 fugal. The supernatant was filtered through 0.22 μ m acetate cellulose filters (Labbox) and
196 then 100 μ L of the supernatant were injected into the chromatographic system. Analyses
197 were carried out by HPLC (Agilent 1200 Series system (Agilent Technologies) with a ag-
198 ilent 1290 Infinity II Diode Array Detector (DAD) to monitor outputs at 230 and 320 nm
199 (for details, see Canals, Arola and Zamora [23]).

Polysaccharide extraction and determination by HRSEC-RID were performed according to Ayestarán, Guadalupe and León [24]. Polysaccharide extraction implied a 5-fold concentration of 10 mL of the finished sparkling wines using a vacuum evaporator, a subsequent precipitation of polysaccharides with 10 mL hydrochloric acid 0.3 mol/L (Panreac) in absolute ethanol, centrifugation, sediment recovery in 1 mL ultrapure water, freezing at -20°C and lyophilization. The lyophilized samples were resuspended in 1 mL of 50 mmol/L ammonium formate (Panreac) and filtered through 0.22 µm acetate cellulose filters before total polysaccharides quantification by high-resolution size-exclusion chromatography (HRSEC) using a refractive index detector (RID) (for details, see Ayestarán, Guadalupe and León [24]).

The procedure followed to measure foaming properties was the Mosalux method [25]. Measurements of maximum height (HM) of the foam after CO₂ injection through the glass frit, and of stable height (HS) during CO₂ injection, were taken. HM represents foamability and HS denotes foam stability. A Mosalux device (Station Oenotechnique de Champagne, Epernay, France) was used to measure these parameters.

2.6 Sensory analysis

A panel of 16 experts did a sensory analysis of the resulting sparkling wines. The panel consisted of six men and 10 women aged between 30 and 60 years. These panelists were all experts in sparkling wine tasting and were previously trained during two preparatory sessions to align their assessment criteria. The visual, aroma, and flavor characteristics were analyzed according to the score sheet for sparkling and pearl wines published by the OIV [27]. The intensity of each attribute was rated on a scale from 0 to 10 with indented anchor points of 'low' and 'high', respectively.

2.7 Statistical analysis

The final residual sugar, ethanol, total and volatile acidities, pH, volatile aroma, total polysaccharide and protein contents and foam properties of "Cava" wines were statistically analyzed by the Statgraphic Plus 5.1. software (Statgraphics Technologies, Inc., The Plains, VA, USA). ANOVA and discriminant analyses were employed. The statistical significance of each considered factor was calculated at $\alpha = 0.05$ by the Student's *t*-test. To simplify the results, a principal component analysis (PCA) and orthogonal projections to the latent structures discriminant analysis were performed with SIMCA, version 10 (MKS Umetrics, Malmo, Sweden). A PCA was used to identify the main factors that explained most of the variance observed from a much larger number of manifest variables.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Kinetics of sugar consumption and ethanol production in capped bottles

The kinetics of glucose and fructose consumption and ethanol production during the second fermentation were recorded to discern if differences between the two yeast preparation methodologies existed. The final sugar and ethanol concentrations were similar in the sparkling wines fermented with the two starter cultures regardless of the yeast culture preparation methodology followed; glucose and fructose were practically exhausted over 30 days, and ethanol increased by 1.5% after 60 days (Figure 1) under both inoculation conditions. The yeast grown on GPY metabolized glucose slightly slower and fructose slightly quicker than the *pie de cuve* yeast, although slightly more residual fructose was found in the GPY-inoculated wines on day 60. From days 7 to 28, the ethanol production kinetics showed that ethanol production was quicker in the wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeast than in those inoculated with the *pie de cuve*-prepared yeast. However, the final ethanol concentration after 60 days was the same in both sparkling wine types.

It is well-known that dry yeast acclimatization by the *pie de cuve* methodology is essential for avoiding cell viability loss in the base wine. Low cell viability may result in either failure to ferment or extended fermentation time [7]. Interesting, the GPY-grown yeasts seemed to properly prepare yeast to cope with wine conditions with no loss of activity. The GPY culture showed higher cell viability and a higher cell concentration than

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the cell preparation from *pie de cuve* (85% vs 60% and 5×10^8 vs 5×10^7 ufc/ml, respectively). It seemed clear that more viable cells could counterbalance yeast stress during the second fermentation because small, but non significant, differences were found in both glucose and fructose consumption and ethanol production (Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Glucose (A) and fructose (B) consumption, and ethanol (C) production kinetics on the first 60 days of the second base wine fermentation performed by *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18–2007 GPY-grown (●) or *pie de cuve*-prepared following the manufacturer’s instructions (▲). Compounds concentrations were determined by HPLC.

GPY contains organic N sources like peptone and yeast extract that can act as protective agents and fermentative enhancers by reducing stress and increasing wine yeast resistance and viability [28-30]. These components also play an important role as a nutrient source because they include a soluble fraction rich in amino acids, vitamins and minerals. Organic N improves growth, biomass production [31,32], cell vitality and survival under adverse conditions [33], and is the preferred N source to maintain metabolic activity in the growth stationary phase [34]. Thus proper nutrition and active growth conditions prior to inoculation in the base wine could determine good behavior during the second fermentation. In addition, N uptake by yeasts during GYP growth could cover the low N availability during the second fermentation. The good N nourishment of cells grown in the GPY medium compensated for the lack of adaptation of the cells prepared by *ped de cuve*.

3.2 Chemical characteristics of sparkling wines

The pH value, titratable and volatile acidities, residual sugars and the ethanol concentrations of the base and finished sparkling wines can be seen in Table 1. All the values obtained from the sparkling wines were similar, no matter what inoculum was used, except for those of titratable acidity. The data comparison of the sparkling and base wine parameters showed significant differences in titratable acidity (bigger in the base wine), and in the residual sugar and ethanol concentrations (higher and lower, respectively, in the base wine).

Titratable acidity was the only parameter that significantly affected sparkling wines. It was 7.65 g/L and 6.30 g/L in the wines inoculated with the GPY-grown and the *ped de cuve*-prepared yeast, respectively. Differences in titratable acidity were not reflected in the corresponding pH values. In fact the wines with higher acidity had higher pH values than those with lower acidity.

Table 1. Chemical parameters of the resulting sparkling wines fermented with the *S. cerevisiae* strain IOC 18-2007 GPY-grown or *ped de cuve*-prepared.

Parameter	Base wine	GPY	<i>Pied de cuve</i>
pH	3.16±0.01 ^a	3.23±0.14 ^a	3.12±0.01 ^a
Titratable acidity (g/L tartaric acid)	8.5±0.01 ^c	7.65±0.21 ^b	6.30±0.21 ^a
Volatile acidity (g/L acetic acid)	0.16±0.01 ^a	0.254±0.085 ^a	0.280±0.109 ^a
Residual sugars	0.88±0.09 ^b	0.36±0.04 ^a	0.42±0.06 ^a
Ethanol (% v/v)	10.97±0.09 ^a	12.37±0.09 ^b	12.35±0.04 ^b

Equal letters indicate lack of statistically significant differences ($P>0.05$)

Differences in titratable acidity could be explained by the different malolactic fermentation occurrence, tartrate salts crystallization or *S. cerevisiae* organic acid production. These distinct scenarios could be influenced by the inoculum preparation procedure. Differences in the acid concentrations of sparkling wines at the end of aging are shown in Table S1. As malolactic fermentation occurred in the overall wines no matter what inoculum was used, this fermentation was not the reason for the differences in titratable acidity. A slightly higher succinic acid concentration and a lower acetic acid concentration of (all non significant) were found in the wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeasts. This means that yeast produced different quantities of organic acids during the second fermentation depending on inoculum preparation. Tartaric acid content was significantly higher in the GPY-inoculated wines. The origin of this acid was not yeast metabolism and the different concentrations found in the wines at the end of aging were due to tartaric salt crystallization. The cause of this phenomenon could lie in the low volume of the GPY yeast culture added to the base wine yeasts containing less potassium than the 4-fold higher volume of *ped de cuve*. The increased ethanol content caused by the second fermenta-

tation could provoke potassium hydrogen tartrate crystallization if wine was not completely stable. When potassium hydrogen tartrate crystallizes, a proportion of the hydrogen tartrate anion is removed from the tartaric acid equilibrium, which leads to displacement toward the release of protons [35], and brings about a simultaneous decrease in titratable acidity and pH. It has been reported that *S. cerevisiae* is able to produce small amounts of organic acids, such as ac. pyruvic, L-lactic, L-(-)malic, fumaric, succinic among others [36]. The production of these acids depends largely on environmental conditions, such as fermentation temperature, sugar and N concentrations, pH [37,38], and also on yeast growth [36,39]. The chemical composition of GPY and the conditions under which *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007 was cultured in the laboratory were very different from the composition of the medium and the conditions used to make the *pie de cuve* in the winery. One reason to explain higher succinic acid production in the GPY-inoculated “Cava” wines was that the yeast grown in GPY had more N supply than in the *pie de cuve* (40-fold more). This would make yeast more capable of producing this acid. Heerde and Radler [40] described that succinic acid production by *S. cerevisiae* was more affected by the N concentration, and the higher the N concentration, the bigger succinic acid production was. Martí-Raga, *et al.* [41] observed that the addition of organic N to the *pie de cuve* affected second fermentation development more than inorganic N addition or the N content in the base wine. A bigger viable and active population of the GPY-grown yeast was introduced into the base wine than when the *pie de cuve*-prepared yeast was used. Several authors have shown that the production of organic acids by *S. cerevisiae* is closely related to growth phase, and occurs mainly during the first hours of growth in both must and synthetic medium [37,39,42].

In any case, these slight differences in the concentration of the analyzed acids only explain part of the difference found in the titratable acidity between the sparkling wines made with the GPY-grown and *pie de cuve*-prepared yeasts. The probable explanation is that the higher titratable acidity of the sparkling wine prepared with the GPY-grown yeasts could be due to the sum of small amounts of many other acids produced by yeasts, such as pyruvic, citric, butyric, and other short- and medium-chain fatty acids, etc.

3.3 Parameters related to yeast autolysis and foaming properties

The total proteins and total polysaccharides concentrations were lower in the sparkling wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeast than in those inoculated with the *pie de cuve*-prepared yeast, although only polysaccharide content showed significant differences (Table 2). The proteins and polysaccharides in the sparkling wines came from the base wine and the cellular autolysis [43]. If we bear in mind that the base wine was the same, then the differences found in the protein and polysaccharides contents in wines would likely be due to distinct autolysis degrees of yeast prepared by differing procedures. Our results indicate that the yeast grown on GPY more slowly developed autolysis than those prepared by *pie de cuve*. Although we did not monitor yeast viability from 60 days after yeast inoculation, the concentration of some volatile compounds related to autolysis support this hypothesis (see Section 3.4).

Table 2. Effect of the *S. cerevisiae* strain IOC 18-2007 inoculum preparation method on foaming properties: foamability (HM) and foam persistence (HS) (expressed as mm), and total polysaccharides and proteins (expressed as mg/L).

Parameter	GPY	<i>Pied de cuve</i>
Total proteins	10.77±0.75 ^a	12.39±0.456 ^a
Total polysaccharides	122.75±0.914 ^a	208.81±31.95 ^b
MH (mm)	66±1 ^b	56±1.4 ^a
SH	61±1 ^b	51±1.4 ^a

Equal letters indicate the absence of statistically significant differences (P>0.05)

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353 Significant differences appeared in foamability (H_M), foam persistence (H_S) and total
 354 polysaccharide concentrations among the sparkling wines (Table 2). The sparkling wines
 355 inoculated with the GPY-grown yeast showed greater foamability (66 mm) and foam per-
 356 sistence (61 mm) than those inoculated with the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeast at the winery.

357 From the exhaustive review of Martínez-Lapuente, *et al.* [44] about the influence of
 358 wine chemical compounds on the foaming properties of sparkling wines, we can deduce
 359 that although some studies have shown positive correlations between proteins and the
 360 H_M parameter [2,45], other authors have not [45,46]. Contradictory results have been rec-
 361 orded about correlations between protein and the H_S parameter [45,46]. Most studies have
 362 found a positive influence of total polysaccharides on both foamability and foam stability
 363 [46], although some authors have reported the opposite [45]. In our case, the wines with a
 364 lower protein content obtained higher H_M and H_S parameter values.

365 Polysaccharides come from the glucans and mannoproteins present in the yeast cell
 366 wall and are released from it during yeast autolysis. Polysaccharides contribute to the
 367 mouth-feel properties of wine by providing ‘mellowness’ and body sensations, but can
 368 also influence sparkling wine’s foam characteristics [10,47]. Although differences in poly-
 369 saccharides content existed between both sparkling wines, there were no positive rela-
 370 tions between polysaccharides concentrations and the H_M and H_S parameters. Contradic-
 371 tory results about the relations between polysaccharides and foam properties have been
 372 published. Moreno-Arribas [48] found that they positively correlated, but Martínez-
 373 Lapuente, *et al.* [49] indicated that polysaccharides were poor foam formers, but good
 374 foam stabilizers. Esteruelas, González-Royo, Kontoudakis, Orte, Cantos, Canals and Za-
 375 mora [45] reported that the high-molecular-weight polysaccharide fraction had a negative
 376 effect on H_M , but they associated this negative contribution to the presence of β -glucans
 377 secreted by *Botrytis cinerea*, and stated that other polysaccharides would probably not
 378 have a negative effect. Martínez-Lapuente, Guadalupe, Ayestarán and Pérez-Magariño
 379 [49] reported that different families of polysaccharides contributed unequally to foam
 380 properties. They found that mannoproteins, glucans, polysaccharides rich in arabinose
 381 and galactose, rhamnogalacturonans type II and homogalacturonans did not influence the
 382 foamability of sparkling wines, but all wine polysaccharides had a positive influence on
 383 foam stability (H_S).

384 3.4 Volatile aroma analysis

385 Thirty volatile compounds were identified in the produced sparkling wines. The con-
 386 centrations of these compounds differed in the sparkling wines fermented with the GPY-
 387 grown and the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeasts (Table 3).

388 **Table 3.** Odor descriptor, odor threshold value, concentration and OAV value for each component
 389 of the aromas found in the sparkling wines fermented with the GPY-grown and the *pied de cuve*-
 390 prepared *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007. The ANOVA analysis results are shown as letters on the data
 391 corresponding to the concentration of aromatic compounds: different letters on the same line denote
 392 significant differences of 95%. OAV calculated by dividing the concentration by the odor threshold
 393 value of the compound.

Group	Volatile compound	Odor de- scriptor	Odor thresh- old values ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	GPY		<i>Pied de cuve</i>	
				Compound concentration $\pm\text{SD}$ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	OAV	Compound concentration $\pm\text{SD}$ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	OAV
Aldehydes	Acetaldehyde	Apple ⁴	5005	184.7 \pm 77.8 ^a	0.4	232.3 \pm 20.7 ^a	0.5
	Benzaldehyde	Almonds ¹	3508	35.7 \pm 5.6 ^b	0.1	ND ^a	ND
	Diacetyl	Butter ³	1002	97.8 \pm 57.8 ^a	1.0	82.5 \pm 72.8 ^a	0.8
	5-Methylfurfural	Spicy ³	200006	184.8 \pm 87.2 ^a	0.0	272.8 \pm 50.2 ^a	0.0
Total alde- hydes			503.0 ^a		587.6 ^b		
Esters	Diethyl glutarate	Fruity ¹	-	30.7 \pm 17.1 ^a	-	23.5 \pm 2.1 ^a	-
	Diethyl succinate	Fruity ¹	12000007	953.5 \pm 280.6 ^a	0.0	825.9 \pm 273.8 ^a	0.0

	Ethyl acetate	Fruity, sweet ¹	123003	134.8±45.2 ^b	0.0	ND ^a	0.0
	Ethyl butyrate	Apple ²	205	73.6±16.3 ^b	3.7	65.4±5.9 ^a	3.3
	Ethyl hexanoate	Fruity, anise ¹	143	100.2±6.3 ^b	7.2	ND ^a	ND
	Ethyl octanoate	Pineapple, pear, floral ¹	25	335.7±139.6 ^a	167.9	362.2±115 ^a	181.1
	Ethyl decanoate	Fruity ¹	2003	496.5±63.5 ^b	2.5	208.6±157.9 ^a	1.0
	Ethyl isovalerate	Fruity ²	32	56.6±0.0 ^b	18.9	ND ^a	ND
	Ethyl lactate	Sour ¹	1550003	34224.2±8016.7 ^a	0.2	28725±3114.9 ^a	0.2
	Hexyl acetate	Fruity, pear ¹	6703	258.8±65.3 ^b	0.4	134.7±11.7 ^a	0.2
	Isobutyl acetate	Solvent ¹	16006	28.7±6.6 ^b	0.0	ND ^a	ND
	Methyl acetate	Fruity ²	4700007	51.0±12 ^a	0.0	43.5±8.6 ^a	0.0
	2- Phenethyl acetate	Pleasant, floral ¹	2503	208.9±89.1 ^b	0.8	86.9±7.4 ^a	0.4
Total esters				36953.2 ^b		30.475,7 ^a	
Acids	Butyric acid	Stale, cheese ²	100005	155.4±27 ^a	0.0	112.2±52.7 ^a	0.0
	2-Ethylhexanoic acid	Herbaceous ¹	-	97.2±10.3 ^b	-	15.9±5.6 ^a	-
	Hexanoic acid	Cheese, fatty, stale ¹	4203	2179.4±492.5 ^a	5.2	1603.9±267.5 ^a	3.8
	Octanoic acid	Cheese, rough, sour ¹	5003	3940.8±943.6 ^b	7.9	2648.5±466.8 ^a	5.3
	Decanoic acid	Fatty ¹	10003	613.1±129.7 ^a	0.6	453.8±180.6 ^a	0.5
	Isobutyric acid	Fatty ¹	2000005	ND ^a	ND	51.7±2 ^b	0.0
Total acids	Isopentanoic acid	Stale ¹	-	184.7±33.3 ^b	-	12.6±2 ^a	-
				7170.6 ^b		4898.6 ^a	
Alcohols	Benzyl alcohol	Citric, fruity ¹	2000006	18.0±9.6 ^a	0.0	27.2±4 ^a	0.0
	2,3-Butanediol	Butter ¹	150 0004	44.2±13.7 ^b	0.0	ND ^a	ND
	1-Butanol	Medicine, alcohol ¹	1500003	47.5±4.3 ^b	0.0	ND ^a	ND
	Isoamyl alcohol	Fusel ¹	300002	40208.9±6545 ^b	1.34	32075.1±6248 ^a	1.1
Total alcohols	2-Phenylethanol	Floral, pollen ¹	140003	7508.1±1625.1 ^b	0.5	5539.7±1005.8 ^a	0.5
				47826.7 ^b		37660 ^a	
Lactones	γ- Butyrolactone	Sweet, toasted, caramel ⁴	500006	814.2±77.7 ^b	0.0	545.4±415.4 ^a	0.0

394 ND: not detected. Odor descriptor references: ¹Jiang and Zhang [50]; ²Francis [51]; ³Gambetta, *et al.* [52]; ⁴Sánchez-Palomo, *et al.* [53]. Odor threshold value references: ⁵Guth [54];
 395 ⁶Aznar, *et al.* [55]; ⁷Zea, *et al.* [56]; ⁸Belitz, *et al.* [57].
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397 The concentrations of benzaldehyde, ethyl esters of acetic, butyric, hexanoic, decanoic and isovaleric acids, hexyl acetate, isobutyl acetate, 2- phenethyl acetate; 2-ethylhexanoic, octanoic, and isopentanoic acids; 2,3-butanediol, 1-butanol, isoamyl alcohol, 2 phenylethanol and γ-butyrolactone were significantly higher in the wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeasts. Only the isobutyric acid concentration was significantly higher in the wines fermented with the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeasts. When considering compound families differences, we found that the total aldehydes content was significantly higher in the wines inoculated with the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeasts, whereas total esters, total fatty acids, total alcohols and lactones were significantly higher in the wines inoculated with the GP-grown yeasts.

407 The formation of aroma compounds by yeast is intrinsically linked with the metabolism of yeast cells [58], but also to the release of some intracellular components during autolysis for sparkling wines [1]. From our results about total protein and polysaccharides, we can deduce that the GPY-grown yeasts were more resistant to autolysis than the *pied de cuve*-prepared ones. The differential concentration of hexyl acetate, 2-phenylethyl acetate (lower in the *pied de cuve*-inoculated Cava wines), diethyl succinate and ethyl decanoate (higher in the *pied de cuve*-inoculated wines) support this hypothesis. Welke, *et al.*
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[59] described how the esterases released by yeast degradation during autolysis led to the hydrolysis of hexyl acetate and 2-phenylethyl acetate and, thus, promoted their reduction. In addition, succinic acid esterification and volatile hydrophobic compounds desorption increase the levels of diethyl succinate and ethyl decanoate as autolysis progresses. Kemp, Alexandre, Robillard and Marchal [1] described diethyl succinate as a good marker of aging because it increased as aging progressed. The N content in GPY is higher than in *pie de cuve*. These results indicate that while preparing yeast, N intake is crucial for second fermentation development [41]. N promotes yeast growth to complete alcoholic fermentation, but also plays a central role in the production of volatile aromas [60,61]. Fairbairn, McKinnon, Musarurwa, Ferreira and Bauer [60] found that minor changes in amino acid concentration not only impact *S. cerevisiae* growth, but also the formation of aromatic compounds.

From the volatile compounds data that showed significant differences, only those compounds with concentrations/odor threshold value (AOVs) ratios above 1 contributed to sparkling wine aroma according to Ferreira, *et al.* [62] and Moyano, *et al.* [63]. By considering the AOVs values, the compounds that contributed to aroma were diacetyl, ethyl butyrate, ethyl hexanoate, ethyl octanoate, ethyl decanoate, ethyl isovalerate, hexanoic and octanoic acids and isoamyl alcohol. The way in which yeast was prepared significantly affected all these compounds except the hexanoic acid concentration.

The sparkling wines fermented with the GPY-grown yeasts contained benzaldehyde, ethyl isovalerate and ethyl hexanoate, which were not detected in the wines fermented with the yeasts prepared at the winery by the *pie de cuve* method. These compounds confer almonds fruity and anise aromas. Taking into account the AOVs, the results suggested that growing yeast cells in GPY was a good option because they generated more esters with a value of OAV>1 than the yeast culture prepared by *pie-de cuve*. However, the high concentrations of fatty acids, such as hexanoic acid and octanoic, and isoamyl alcohol in the wines fermented with the GPY-grown yeasts could contribute negatively because they confer fusel and fatty aromas [13].

A PCA analysis of the volatile data was done to know if the yeast preparation strategy discriminated sparkling wines. Figure 2 shows the plots of the two principal component loadings and the two principal component scores. Sparkling wines are separated on the plane, which means that wines' volatile composition differed significantly depending on the yeast preparation methodology that had taken place. In Fig. 2A, the wines fermented with the GPY-grown yeasts are to the left of the PC1 component, while the wines fermented with the *pie de cuve*-prepared yeasts are to the right of this component. Figure 2B shows the arrangement of the different aromatic compounds on the plane. This arrangement provides a clue of the main differences in wine volatile composition concerning the applied yeast starter culture preparation methodology.

3.5 Sensory analysis

The sensory analysis of the sparkling wines was performed by evaluating the visual, aroma and flavor characteristics. The score for wines are displayed in Fig. 3. There were no significant differences in the visual and flavor scores between the wines inoculated with both the GPY-grown yeasts and *pie de cuve* prepared yeasts. Significant differences were found in the aroma scores. The wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeasts obtained a significantly lower score (4.89 points) than those inoculated with the *pie de cuve*-prepared yeasts (5.89 points). One explanation for this result is that part of the sensory panel was made up of staff members from the winery where the experiment took place. These tasters are more accustomed to the "Cava" aromas produced by the *pie de cuve* methodology, which is the one they normally use and, therefore, the aromatic deviations from this profile were less appreciated. Although a higher esters content was found in the wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeasts, and these compounds conferred wine a fruitier aroma, it is also noted that the concentrations of fatty acids and higher alcohols

(or fusel alcohols) in these wines were higher than in those inoculated with the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeast. These aroma families contribute negatively to aroma [64].

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Figure 2. Principal component analysis (PCA) of volatile compounds in sparkling wines inoculated with the GPY-grown and *pied de cuve*-prepared *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007. The analysis was performed with the SIMCA software, version 10 (MKS Umetrics, Malmo, Sweden): (A) plot of the two principal component scores; (B) plot of the two principal component loadings.

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Figure 3. Sensory evaluation of the sparkling wines obtained with the two yeast starter cultures for the second fermentation, displayed as means and LSD intervals at 95%. Blue depicts the GPY-grown yeasts and red the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeasts. Different letters indicate significant differences between wines. The sensorial panel was made up of 16 persons.

4. Conclusions

This study determined the impact of yeast culture preparation on not only second fermentation development, but also on the organoleptic characteristics of the final product after 9 months of aging. We investigated differences in the protein and polysaccharides concentrations, foamability and foam stability, volatile composition and sensoriality of the wines inoculated with the yeast *S. cerevisiae* IOC 18-2007, which was GPY-grown and *pied de cuve*-prepared.

In both cases, sugar exhaustion was completed in less than 60 days, ethanol concentrations were similar and no significant differences were found in the fermentation kinetics. The sparkling wines analysis showed higher significant values for total acidity, foamability, foam persistence and content of total polysaccharides in the wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeast. Regarding the concentration of volatile compounds, higher contents of esters, alcohols and fatty acids with an OAV >1 were obtained in the sparkling wines inoculated with the GPY-grown yeast. The sensory analysis indicated no significant differences for the visual or flavor parameters. However in aromatic terms, the sparkling wine inoculated with the *pied de cuve*-prepared yeast was better scored than those inoculated with the GPY-grown yeast.

Both sparkling wines were produced with the same base wine and were inoculated with the same yeast strain. The only factor that differentiated them was the way in which yeast was prepared before wine inoculation.

Additional research is necessary to confirm if the differences in viability, autolysis and metabolisms of the yeasts prepared in either GPY or *pied de cuve* could explain the differences found in sparkling wines.

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